

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

To Cite:

Anorue, D.N. Caecal Microbial Population, Oxidative Stress and Sensory Evaluation of Grower Pigs Fed Cassava Peel-Maize Cob Meal. *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal* 2024; Vol 4, Issue 1, pp. 133-138. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737169>

Author Affiliation:

¹Department of Animal Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

***Corresponding Author**

¹Department of Animal Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

Email: anorued@gmail.com

Peer-Review History

Received: 2nd June, 2024

Reviewed & Revised: 3rd/June / 2024 to 12th July 2024

Accepted: 13th July 2024

Published: July 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSN: xxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/integatemind-journal>

Ethics

Animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

License: **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**

Caecal Microbial Population, Oxidative Stress and Sensory Evaluation of Grower Pigs Fed Cassava Peel-Maize Cob Meal

Daniel Nnadozie Anorue ^{1*}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12737169>

ABSTRACT

This experiment was carried out to examine the caecal microbial population, oxidative stress and sensory evaluation of grower pigs fed cassava peel-maize cob meal. 32 male cross bred grower pigs (Landrace × Duroc) were stratified based on their body weight and distributed into four treatments with 4 replicates consisting of 2 pigs each. Pigs in treatment 1 was given basal diet without cassava peel – maize cob meal (SCPM) while SCPM was used to replace maize at 40 %, 50 % and 60 % in treatment 2, 3 and 4 respectively. A completely randomized design model was adopted and the experiment lasted for 3 months while diet was formulated according to the requirement of pigs according to NRC (1994). Result showed that *Lactobacillus* and *Escherichia coli* count were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by the treatment except for *Salmonella* sp, *Staphylococcus* and *Micrococcus* sp count ($P > 0.05$). Total antioxidant capacity, catalase, superoxide dismutase, glutathione dismutase and malondialdehyde follow similar pattern as values were higher in treatment 3 and 4, intermediate in treatment 2 and lower in treatment 1. Sensory evaluation of colour and flavor which varied from 5.77 – 6.98 and 5.30 – 6.13 respectively were significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected expect tenderness, juiciness, texture and overall acceptability were not different among the treatment ($P > 0.05$). In conclusion, SCPM was used to replace maize at up to 60 % without compromising the performance and health status of animals.

Keywords: Cassava peel; Maize cob; Phytochemicals; Pigs; Food safety; Sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the major constraints of the development of poultry industry in Nigeria is the high cost of feeds. Maize constitutes about 60 % of feed which also serves as food for many households in Nigeria (Nuhu et al., 2008). Competition between man and livestock for maize, soya beans among others is often responsible for high cost of these ingredients (Odunsi, 2005). This challenge promoted the need for an alternative feed stuffs to curb the increasing incidence of low protein intake in developing countries, improve food security and livestock sustainability (John, 2024; Mbajiorgu et al., 2011). Among the potential alternative agro-industrial product (unconventional feedstuff) is cassava peels and maize cob (Daniel, 2024). Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is a major staple food grain throughout the world, particularly in Africa, Latin America and Asia (Marcu et al., 2013). The maize grain is a major feed grain and a standard component of livestock diets where it is used as a source of energy (Marcu et al., 2013). Other grains are typically compared to maize when their nutritional value particularly energy content is estimated (Ghazalah et al., 2012). According to Marcu et al. (2013), maize contains 8.9 % crude protein and 3400.7 metabolizable energy. Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) belongs to the genus *Manihot* of the order Euphorbiaceae. It is said to have been introduced into West Africa from Brazil by the early Portuguese explorers. Cassava is the most productive tuber crop in terms of energy yield per unit land area (Faniyi, 2002).

SHERWAN
Publishers

Cassava peels are the back cover of the cassava tuber which is manually removed using sharp knives with little or no pulp in the peel. These peels are often two layers; the outer brownish and relatively thin rind and grayish, whitish or light brown inner and comparatively large rind. When processed for inclusion in diet, it is referred to as cassava peel meal (Edache et al., 2012). Cassava peel is one of the agro-industrial by-product that is readily available in countries where cassava is cultivated and processed into food for man. The peels account for about 10-15 % of the tuber by weight. It contains about 5.00 - 5.98 % crude protein (Idowu et al., 2006). There are limitations on the use of cassava products in poultry diet because of its dustiness, milling difficulty, reduction in feed intake and an appreciable content of anti-nutritional factor which is Hydrocyanic acid (HCN) (Salami, 1999). However, Odunsi (2003); Blandon et al. (2015) reported several processing methods to enhance the feeding value of cassava products; like parboiling, soaking in water and sun drying (fermentation). Omoikhoje et al. (2008) have reported on the extensive use of cassava peel meal as cheaper substitutes for maize in the diet of monogastrics. The by-product represents a potential source of energy and minerals for livestock feeding when properly collected and processed. According to Oladunjoye et al. (2017) sun dried cassava peel contains 3118.42 kcal/kg of metabolizable energy, 11.61% of crude protein, 8.01 % of crude fiber, 2.050% of ether extract, 6.21% of total ash and 72.08% of nitrogen free extract. Previous reports by Daniel et al. (2024a); Daniel (2024b), has shown that dried cassava peel – maize cob mixture can be used to replace maize up to 30 % and 60 % in weaner and grower pigs respectively without causing any deleterious effect on their growth performance. Ojediran et al. (2022) also reported that processed cassava peel at 20 % significantly influenced blood parameters without compromising the health status of pigs. However, there is paucity of information on the use of cassava peel-maize cob meal on the ceecal microbial population, oxidative stress indices and sensory evaluation of grower pigs. This research will influence livestock sustainability and improve protein intake for consumers.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Site of the research

This study was conducted at the University of Abuja Teaching and Research Farm, Main Campus, along Airport Road, Gwagwalada, Abuja, Nigeria; the Department of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture. Gwagwalada, situated between latitudes 8°57' and 8°55'N and longitudes 7°05' and 7°06'E (NPC, 2006).

2.2. Gathering and processing of cassava peels and maize cob

Freshly processed cassava peels were collected from Gwagwalada market and gathered in a sack for 3 days. Test ingredients were transferred to the department of Biological science for proper identification and samples were assigned voucher numbers AA/09E/2020 and AB/09F/2020 for cassava peel and maize cob respectively. Thereafter, they were dried separately under the sun for 15 days until a constant sample weight was obtained and hammer milled to obtain cassava peel meal and maize cob meal before it was mixed in a ratio of 1: 1.

2.3. Animal care and experimental design

32 male cross bred grower pigs (Landrace × Duroc) were used for the trial. On arrival, animals were fed basal diet which was formulated to meet their nutrient requirement according to National Research Council's recommendation in 2002 and placed on quarantine for 14 days. During this period, animals were given dewormer (Ivermectin) against parasites. Thereafter pigs were stratified based on their body weight and distributed into four treatments with 4 replicates consisting of 2 pigs each. A completely randomized design model was adopted and the experiment lasted for 3 months. Good biosecurity was maintained during the trial and animals were given free access to feed and clean water.

2.4. Experimental procedure

Sundried cassava peel and maize cob meal (SCPM) in ratio 1:1 was incorporated into the experimental diet to replace maize. Treatment 1 (T1) control diet (without SCPM); T2 (40 % replacement); T3 (50 % replacement), T4 (60 % replacement) presented in Table 1.

Table 1:Gross composition of the experimental diets

Ingredients	T1 (0 %)	T2 (40 %)	T3 (50 %)	T4 (60 %)
Maize	60.00	36.00	30.00	24.00
Wheat offal	8.00	8.00	8.00	8.00
Soya beans	17.30	17.30	17.30	17.30
Groundnut cake	7.00	7.00	7.00	7.00
CPMCM	0.00	24.00	30.00	36.00
Bone meal	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Limestone	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50

Ingredients	T1 (0 %)	T2 (40 %)	T3 (50 %)	T4 (60 %)
Methionine	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Lysine	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Enzymes	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.03
Salt	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Determined analysis (%)				
Crude protein	16.44	15.13	15.04	15.00
Energy (Kcal/kg)	2800.1	2758.6	2760.2	2768.1

*Vitamin A, 8,000 I.U., Vitamin E, 5 mg, Vitamin D3, 3000 I.U., Vitamin K, 3 mg, Vitamin B2, 5.5 mg, Niacin, 25 mg, Vitamin B12, 16 mg, Choline chloride, 120 mg, Mn, 5.2 mg, Zn, 25 mg, Cu, 2.6 mg, Folic acid, 2 mg, Fe, 5 mg, Pantothenic acid, 10 mg, Biotin, 30.5 mg, and antioxidant, 56 mg are provided as a premix per kilogramme meal.

2.5. Data analysis

Data collected (Immune response, microbial analysis and sensory evaluation) were analyzed using the general linear model procedures of Statistical Analysis Systems software (SAS) with the model containing treatments. Differences between treatment means were separated using Duncan's test (SAS, 2001). Significant differences were declared at $P < 0.05$.

2.6. Microbial examination of the caecal microorganism

Caecal samples were taken for microbiological analysis from six pigs per treatment at the end of the experiment. To identify the intestinal bacteria, examination was done using a Microplate Reader (DR – 200 BC – LED bulb). Samples were combined with peptone reagent on different agar and incubated for eight hours at 35 degrees Celsius. Miccom automated kit and adjusted at an ambient temperature range of 15 to 40 °C; input voltage of 100 to 200 VAC at 50 to 60 Hz; output voltage of 24 VAC with direct current; visible chamber made of OG550 glass filter; LED protector made of transparent polycarbonate with a 1.4462 stainless steel body and lever.

2.7. Examining oxidative stress

Six pigs per treatment had their livers sampled (from pigs used for carcass inquiry). Liver samples were tested with a NEXRO kit (Model 81-09A, India) after being submerged in potassium solution. The DNPH solution, hematoxylin, wash buffer, and antigen retrieval buffer are the parts of the kit. The output unit or display was used to gauge the oxidative detection of glutathione peroxidase, catalase, reduced glutathione, superoxide dismutase, and malondialdehyde.

2.8. Sensory assessment

Thirty panelists performed the sensory evaluation of cooked samples of minced meat from the thigh muscles of six pigs per treatment (pigs used for carcass evaluation). The panelists assessed colour, juiciness, flavour, tenderness, and overall acceptability among other parameters. Every meat sample was coded and shown to the panel members one after the other. To prevent spills, each participant cleaned their mouth after handling each sample of meat. A nine-point hedonic scale was used by the panelists to assign scores: (i) Dislike excessively (ii) Very much dislike, (iii) Moderately dislike (iv) Dislike somewhat (v), Intermediate, (vi) Like somewhat (vii), Like moderately, (viii) Like very much (ix) Like excessively.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Caecal microbial population of grower pigs fed dried cassava peel – maize cob meal (SCPM)

Caecal microbial population of grower pigs fed dried cassava peel – maize cob meal is presented in Table 2. Microbial count on *Lactobacillus sp.* and *Escherichia coli* were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by the treatments except for *Micrococcus luteus*, *Staphylococcus sp.* and *Salmonella sp.* population ($P > 0.05$). *Lactobacillus sp.* count were higher in T2, T3 and T4 than T1. Conversely, *Escherichia coli* population were greater ($P < 0.05$) in T1 relative to other treatments.

Table 2: Caecal microbial population of grower pigs fed dried cassava peel – maize cob meal

Specifications	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
No of animals	8	8	8	8	-
<i>Lactobacillus sp.</i>	2.21 ^b	4.08 ^a	4.16 ^a	4.56 ^a	0.05
<i>Escherichia coli.</i>	3.93 ^a	1.45 ^b	1.29 ^b	1.00 ^b	0.01
<i>Staphylococcus sp.</i>	1.88	1.57	1.50	1.47	0.01

Specifications	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	2.94	2.76	2.55	2.43	0.02
<i>Micrococcus luteus.</i>	1.78	1.89	1.80	1.71	0.01

Note: Means on the same column with different superscripts are significant ($P<0.05$); T1: 0 % SPCM; T2: 40 % SPCM; T3: 50 % SPCM; T4: 60 % SPCM; SEM: standard error of mean

3.2. Oxidative stress of grower pigs fed dried cassava peel – maize cob meal

Oxidative stress of grower pigs fed dried cassava peel – maize cob meal is presented in Table 3. Total antioxidant capacity and catalase were higher ($P<0.05$) in T3 and T4 than in other treatments. Superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione dismutase (GSH) and malondialdehyde values varied from 42.06 - 56.87 (U/mL), 140.8 - 168.93 (U/mL) and 7.92 - 11.40 (U/mL) respectively. SOD, GSH and MDA values were influenced ($P<0.05$) by the treatments.

Table 3: Oxidative stress of grower pigs fed dried cassava peel – maize cob meal

Specifications	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
No of animals	8	8	8	8	-
TAC (U/mL)	11.56 ^c	15.76 ^b	17.20 ^a	18.67 ^a	0.81
Catalase (U/mL)	52.74 ^c	57.78 ^b	62.56 ^a	63.05 ^a	2.92
SOD (U/mL)	43.74 ^b	42.06 ^b	43.09 ^b	56.87 ^a	2.50
GSH (U/mL)	168.93 ^a	146.2 ^b	140.8 ^c	140.1 ^c	8.77
MDA (nmol/mL)	11.40 ^a	8.08 ^b	8.00 ^b	7.92 ^b	0.65

Note: Means on the same column with different superscripts are significant ($P<0.05$); T1: 0 % SPCM; T2: 40 % SPCM; T3: 50 % SPCM; T4: 60 % SPCM; SEM: standard error of mean; TAC: total antioxidant capacity; SOD: superoxide dismutase; GSH: glutathione dismutase; MDA: malondialdehyde

3.3. Organoleptic assessment of grower pigs fed maize cob-cassava peel meal

Table 4 shows the organoleptic assessment of grower pigs fed SPCM. The diets had significant effect on the colour and flavor ($p<0.05$) while no significant effect ($P>0.05$) was observed on tenderness, juiciness, texture, and overall acceptability. The observation on colour and flavor revealed that values were higher in T2, T3 and T4 and lower in T1 ($P<0.05$). All treatments were statistically superior for flavor except those fed treatment 1.

Table 4: Organoleptic assessment of grower pigs fed SPCM

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
No of animals	8	8	8	8	-
Tenderness	6.10	6.11	6.17	6.20	0.28
Colour	5.77 ^b	6.85 ^a	6.92 ^a	6.98 ^a	0.22
Flavor	5.30 ^b	6.10 ^a	6.11 ^a	6.13 ^a	0.18
Juiciness	6.91	6.93	6.96	6.98	0.25
Texture	5.62	5.50	5.73	5.77	0.29
Overall acceptability	6.67	6.69	6.81	6.83	0.21

Note: Means on the same column with different superscripts are significant ($P<0.05$); T1: 0 % SPCM; T2: 40 % SPCM; T3: 50 % SPCM; T4: 60 % SPCM; SEM: standard error of mean

4. DISCUSSION

The occurrence of *Staphylococcus sp.* and *Lactobacillus sp.* in the caecum samples of the pigs confirms the existence of a normal microbiota environment as these organisms exist under the normal microbiota of the vertebrate gastrointestinal tract (Willey *et al.*, 2008). There was no difference in total *Salmonella sp.*, *Micrococcus luteus* and *Staphylococcus sp.* count across treatments. This is contrary to the report of Aroet *et al.* (2017), who observed an increase in the faecal bacterial count of pigs fed a cassava-based diet. The non-significant difference in total *Salmonella sp.* and *Staphylococcus sp.* count obtained in this study implies that SPCM influenced the microflora in a similar pattern just as the maize-based diet due to the availability of readily utilizable nutrients. The reduction in *Escherichia coli* observed with the inclusion of SPCM in the diet of pigs is associated with the acidic environment created as a result

of short-chain fatty acid produced by dietary fibre fermentation in the gut capable of inhibiting the growth of some intestinal pathogens such as *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella sp.* and *Clostridium sp.* (Montagne *et al.*, 2003). According to Daniel (2024), SPCM contains phyto-constituents such as alkaloids and tannins which are capable of killing pathogenic organisms in the gut of animals. This study reveals the utilize ability of SCPM by growing pigs without causing any negative effect on microflora. In addition, *Lactobacillus sp.* population were higher in pigs fed SCPM compared to the control group. The significant increase in their population will decrease pathogenic organism count thus preventing dysbiosis (Szermeret *et al.*, 2017; John, 2024).

Oxidative stress report obtained in this current experiment reveals that pigs in T3 and T4 showed higher values of superoxide dismutase and catalase and reduced melanodialdehyde (MDA) concentration in comparison those in T1. John (2024); Ojediran *et al.* (2024), observed that phytochemicals especially tannins and flavonoids can scavenge free radicals, increase antioxidant enzymes and inhibit lipid peroxidation. However, evaluation on the phytochemical constituents of SPCM reveals the presence of these phytochemicals (alkaloids, tannins, saponins, flavonoids amongst others) which gives an advantage to animals fed with the test ingredients (Daniel, 2023). Superoxide dismutase play an important role in protecting cells from damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS), but this process requires dietary supply of the appropriate nutrients (John, 2024; Alagbe, 2024). Such antioxidant effects would be expected to improve the health of pigs as well as the nutritional quality of meat (Alagbe, 2024; John, 2024). Melanodialdehyde is one of the most frequently used indicators of lipid peroxidation associated with oxidative stress (Aksuet *et al.*, 2010; Musa *et al.*, 2021). Catalase is one of the main antioxidative enzymes in mammals, and these enzymes could reduce hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and organic hydroperoxides (Wang, 2006; Shittu *et al.*, 2021). Their activities are commonly used to assess body antioxidative status (Tao *et al.*, 2005; Adewale *et al.*, 2021). This is inconsonance with the report of Ajuonuma and Uchendu (2013) who stated that, with increasing cassava peel meal inclusions, diets led to a slight increase in the values of total antioxidant capacity and catalase in growing pigs.

The replacement of maize with dried cassava peel – maize cob mixture had an influence on the sensory attributes of the grower meat. The values obtained in 40 %, 50 % and 60 % SPCM were similar compared to other group. This implied that the taste of panelists could not differentiate the meat samples. The SCPM based diets improved the juiciness and tenderness of the meat. Therefore, SCPM promoted overall acceptability of meat from weaner pig without any deleterious influence on the meat quality. Breidenstein and Carpenter (2013) reported that colour, flavour, juiciness and tenderness are the essential parameters of the eating quality of meat. Also, Pippen *et al.* (2019) reported that the components responsible for flavour are from the lean portion and dissolved in the fat during cooking. However, Awosanya *et al.* (2000) observed that the only factor which was responsible for consumers' overall acceptability of rabbit meat is the age at which the animal is slaughtered. Therefore, the younger the age of the livestock, the more acceptable is its meat. Moreover, juiciness is important in the tenderness of meat because it provides lubrication to the consumers, and enhances mouth feel (Owens *et al.*, 2004). Tenderness had been reported as a major quality determinant and probably the most essential sensory characteristic of meat (Deatherage, 2003). Tenderness score followed a similar trend as juiciness and flavour. Smulders *et al.* (2011) reported that meat tenderization is a multifactorial process which depends on a number of biological and environmental factors. The utilization of SCPM increased the degree of tenderness, as assessed by the taste of panelists. This agreed with the findings of Omojola and Adesehinwa (2007) who reported that exogenous enzyme increased the degree of tenderness of breast meat from pigs. However, the result for texture did not agree with the reports of the same author who observed that these parameters were affected by the by the inclusion of enzyme pig diets.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, Sundried cassava peel and maize cob meal (SCPM) can be used as a potential agro industrial waste that can be used to replace maize due to its nutritional composition and valuable phytoconstituents with therapeutic importance. Replacement of maize with SPCM up to 60 % had a positive influence on the microbial flora in the ceacum, prevents oxidative stress and sensory quality of animal's meat without having any negative effect on their health status.

Ethical approval

Animal guidelines were followed in this study for species observation and identification (ANSJ/005C).

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

REFERENCES AND NOTES

1. Adewale, A.O., Alagbe, J.O., and Adeoye, A.O. (2021). Dietary supplementation of Rauvolfia vomitoria root extract as a phytogetic feed additive in growing rabbit diets: Haematology and serum biochemical indices. *International Journal of Organic Technology*, 3(3), 1-12.
2. Alagbe, J.O. (2023). Investigating the effects of dietary supplementation of Eucalyptus camaldulensis essential oil on the growth performance, nutrient digestibility and caecal fermentation of weaned rabbits. *Research in Agriculture and Veterinary Science*, 7(3), 139-148.
3. Alagbe, J.O. (2023). Investigating the effects of dietary supplementation of Eucalyptus camaldulensis essential oil on haemato-biochemical indices, immune response and oxidative stress of weaned rabbits. *International Journal of Agricultural and Animal Production*, 4(1), 34-46.
4. Alagbe, O.J. (2024). Novel phyto-genics' impact on weaned pig's growth performance, haematology, and serum biochemical indicators. *Black Sea Journal of Agriculture*, 7(2), 82-89.
5. Alagbe, O.J., Daniel, N.A., Shittu, M.D., Emiola, A., Akande, T., and Adegoke, A.E. (2023). Impact of dietary supplementation of Carica papaya essential oil on the blood chemistry of broiler chickens. *Scientific Letters*, 11(3), 105-110.
6. Aro, S.O., Aletor, V.A., and Oladunmoye, M.K. (2017). Feeding microbe-fermented cassava tuber wastes modulates gut microbiota and faecal characteristics of growing pigs. *Fermentation Technology*, 8(2), 26-33.
7. Blandon, J.C., Hamady, G.A.A., and Abdel-Moneim, M.A. (2015). The effect of partial replacement of yellow corn by banana peels with and without enzymes on broiler's performance and blood parameters. *Journal of Animal Science*, 4(2), 10-19.
8. Blandon, J.C., Hamady, G.A.A., and Abdel-Moneim, M.A. (2015). The effect of partial replacement of yellow corn by banana peels with and without enzymes on broiler's performance and blood parameters. *Journal of Animal and Poultry Science*, 4(1), 10-19.
9. Daniel, N.A., Friday, U., and Alagbe, O.J. (2023). Investigating the effects of pawpaw (Carica papaya) essential oil dietary supplementation on the growth performance and carcass characteristics of broilers. *Research in Agriculture and Veterinary Science*, 7(3), 164-174.
10. Edache, J.A., Yisa, A.G., and Okpala, E.J. (2012). Effect of replacing maize with yam peel meal on short-term laying performance of Japanese quails (Coturnix coturnix japonica). *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 11(7), 516-519.
11. Faniyi, G.F. (2002). Replacement of wheat offal with untreated citrus pulp in broiler chick diets. *Tropical Animal Production Investigations*, 5(95), 100.
12. Ghazalah, A.A., Gomaa, I.A., and Hyam, T. (2002). The use of date stone meal (DSM) and potato by-product meal (PBM) as non-conventional energy feed sources in Nile tilapia Oreochromis niloticus diets. In *The 1st Scientific Conference of the Egyptian Aquaculture Society*, El-Arish, North Sinai, Egypt, pp. 13-15.
13. John, A.O. (2024). Clerodendrum splendens leaf extract supplementation in weaner rabbits: impact on growth performance, haematology and intestinal microbial population. *Corrado: Agricultural Biological Research*, 1(1), 21-31.
14. John, A.O. (2024). Effect of coconut shell extract on the growth performance and some haemato-biochemical parameters of broiler chicken. *Brazilian Journal of Science*, 3(6), 82-95.
15. John, A.O. (2024). Growth performance, haemato-biochemical indices of broiler chicken fed Aristolochia indica as a phytogetic feed additive. *Corrado: Agricultural Biological Research*, 1(1), 42-53.
16. John, A.O., Muritala, S.D., Aduragbemi, Y.A., Kadiri, C.M., Bamiloye, S.O., Jummai, C., and Effiong, E. (2024). The approximate mineral and phytochemical content of the leaves, stem bark and roots of Pterocarpus erinaceus in India. *Corrado: Agricultural Biological Research*, 1(1), 32-41.
17. Marcu, A., Vacaru-Opriş, I., Dumitrescu, G., Marcu, A., Petculescu, C.L., Nicula, M., Dronca, D., and Kelcirov, B. (2013). Effect of diets with different energy and protein levels on breast muscle characteristics of broiler chickens. *Animal Science and Biotechnologies*, 46, 333-340.
18. Mbajjorgu, C.A., Ng'ambi, J.W., and Norris, D. (2011). Effect of varying dietary energy to protein ratio level on growth and productivity of indigenous Venda chickens. *Asian Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 6, 344-354.
19. Musa, B., Alagbe, J.O., Adegbite, M.B., and Omokore, E.A. (2020). Growth performance, caeca microbial population and immune response of broiler chicks fed aqueous extract of Balanites aegyptiaca and Alchornea cordifolia stem bark mixture. *Universal Journal of Research and Technology*, 2(2), 13-21.
20. Nuhu, B., Abba, A., and Amina, L. (2008). The profitability of broiler chickens raised on graded levels of maize offal and wheat offal-based diets. *Proceedings of the 13th Annual Conference of the Animal Science Association of Nigeria (ASAN)*, Nigeria, pp. 298-302.
21. Odunsi, A. (2005). Response of laying hens and growing broilers to the dietary inclusion of mango (Mangifera indica L.) seed kernel meal. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 37(2), 139-150.
22. Ojediran, T.K., Emiola, I.A., Durojaye, V., and Alagbe, O.J. (2024). Proximate, vitamin and GC/MS profiling of Kigelia africana fruit powder. *Corrado: Agricultural and Biological Sciences*, 1(1), 13-20.
23. Ojediran, T.K., Emiola, I.A., Durojaye, V., and Alagbe, O.J. (2024). Analysis of Kigelia africana fruits powder antioxidant and phytochemical properties. *Brazilian Journal of Science*, 3(7), 38-49.
24. Owen, O.J., Liu, N.O., and Amakiri, A.O. (2010). Japanese quail (Coturnix coturnix Japonica): Its potentials, opportunities, and challenges. *Proceedings of the 31st Annual Conference of the Nigerian Society for Animal Production*, 14-17th March 2010, University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, pp. 333-335.
25. Shittu, M.D., Alagbe, J.O., Adejumo, D.O., Ademola, S.G., Abiola, A.O., Samson, B.O., and Ushie, F.T. (2021). Productive performance, caeca microbial population and immune-modulatory activity of broiler chicks fed different levels Sida acuta leaf extract in replacement of antibiotics. *Bioinformation and Proteomics Academy Journal*, 5(1), 000143.
26. Willey, J.M., Woolverton, L.M., Sherwood, L.M., Prescott, M., and Harley, J.P. (2008). *Prescott, Harley, and Klein's Microbiology* (7th Edn). McGraw-Hill, New York, USA. ISBN: 9780072992915.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s). Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.